

DAMAGE VISUAL INDICATION SYSTEM FOR POLYMER COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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1 Introduction

Due to specific properties and excellent mechanical possibilities polymer composite structures are widely used in different applications. Non-destructive testing methods for such elements are well studied, at the same time, the visual inspection stays more fastest, cheapest and most commonly used anyway.

In the present work the concept of structural health monitoring of composite elements during its assembling, transportation, and exploitation is presented. The concept is based on an integration of microcapsules into the thin layer, which could be later placed on the top of the composite surface as well into the composite, as a structural element. Two types of microcapsules, containing leuco dyes and activator are colour neutral. Subjected by an external loads shells of microcapsules burst, components get in a contact and chemical reaction is accompanied by a colour change. Thus, place of the applied load could be visually identified.

The general aim of the study was to improve exploitation safety and simplify structural testing process of polymer composites in constructions.

The specific aim of the study was to develop a damage visual indication system for polymer composite and validate it.

2 Materials

Microcapsules (MC) with leuco dye and with dye developer, as water-based dispersions were supplied by *Papierfabrik August Koehler Ag.*, Germany. The microcapsules are made from melamine-formaldehyde resin. As a leuco dye, the Crystal violet lactone was used.

As a base material, glass fabric *Aeroglass plain*, 130 g/m² and nylon fabric 84 g/m² were used, in

accordance of further application; the first one was integrated into the composite, the other one was used as an external layer.

3 Experiments

The experimental part of the work was divided into 3 sections: the study of microcapsules, preparation of the DVIS for external use and the study of its properties, and preparation of the DVIS as an internal layer with subsequent testing.

3.1 Microcapsules

For the use of microcapsules as a part of the damage visual indication system, examination of the microcapsules was performed. Physical parameters like size and shell thickness of microcapsules were defined by SEM analysis. Thermal stability of microcapsules was measured by TGA, as well ability to change colour after chemical reaction of both encapsulated components was measured. Mechanical properties of microcapsules were defined by AFM testing, as well compared with results obtained by evaluation of effective properties of the assemble of m/c. Results from the direct and indirect testing were compared and applied for modelling.

3.2 DVIS as external layer

The nylon fabric using rubber roller was impregnated on the Teflon substrate with the mixture of two components in ration 1:1. After impregnation, the nylon fabric was dried for at least 6 h at room temperature to remove the excess liquid. As a method that holds microcapsules on the surface of the fabric the laminating process was selected. Thus, the appearance and barrier properties of DVIS were improved. It is more "friendly" to manipulations, like transportation and fixating. By using cover sheets with different thickness is possible to vary the

threshold of DVIS sensitivity to external loads. The optimal amount of MC, comparing to nominal concentration was defined. Comparing dyes with different colours, the colour with the best visual response was selected. Kinetics of colour change after the applied load for the range of temperatures was defined.

3.3 DVIS as internal layer

Similar procedure as for external layer was applied for the glass fabric impregnation. The model composite with integrated DVIS was assembled by vacuum bagging with the subsequent laying of all layers. The pressing and subsequent curing of plane composite specimens were performed in vacuum under 0.4 bars at a temperature of 40-60 °C for 20 h. Applying this procedure specimens with different protective coating were prepared and tested to define the dependence of the threshold of visual response on the thickness of the protective. To evaluate effect of integrated DVIS on mechanical properties of composite two identical specimens were prepared with the difference in the medium layer; in the first one, there was DVIS, in the second one DVIS was substituted with the same fabric layer without any microcapsules. Both specimens were tested on interlaminar shear strength.

Results

Diameter of microcapsules was defined as $D1 \approx 7 \mu\text{m}$ for m/c with dye and $D2 \approx 2 \mu\text{m}$ for m/c with developer. Shell thickness for both types of m/c is $h \approx 0.10 \mu\text{m}$. Microcapsules showed thermal stability till 350 °C, while an ability to change colour kept only till 150 °C. Elastic modulus of microcapsule shell material was defined as $3.5 \pm 0.3 \text{ GPa}$. Effective properties of microcapsules defined by the inverse calculation basically were influenced by the matrix material were m/c were dispersed.

For the DVIS was defined that a decrease of the amount of MC in two times, comparing to 40% concentration in reference suspension, allows observing the same visual response after applied load. Comparing dye with red, blue, green, black colours, was defined: the same applied load leads to different brightness of colour response. Sensitive layers with blue and green colour m/c showed a brighter visual response after applied load.

It was defined that temperature in the range from -20 till +38 °C does not affect on the kinetics of colour

change (visual response) after applied load; for all specimens the maximal visual response was reached in 10-15 sec and the brightness practically remained unchanged. Integrated into composite DVIS reduced the interlaminar shear strength roughly twofold.

Conclusions

In the present work technology of producing of the damage visual indication system was developed. Microcapsules could be successfully used as a part of the DVIS for composites and other structures, where external load is critical for further exploitation. Reducing the required amount of microcapsules for visual indication will reduce the price and weight of the DVIS layer. The temperature interval of the exploitation is quite wide, as well, very quick reaction on applied load allows to use such DVIS for the inspection of big surfaces. Application of DVIS as an internal part of composite should be investigated more detailed.